

POP
AI

Pop art emerged as an artform in the post-WW2 period in the US and the UK. It challenged the traditions, aesthetics and values of fine art by incorporating elements from popular culture (hence the term 'pop'). Artists' creative practice sought to comment on mass commodity culture and its centrality in Western economies, as well as addressing contemporary political issues. A key concern was to bring fine art to the level of the everyday, blurring the boundaries between 'high' and 'low' art and making it accessible to mainstream publics. Pop art often used bright colours, particularly the primary colours of red, blue and yellow. Another common feature was the use of repeated imagery, employing techniques such as silk screening and collage involving words, symbols and photos from contemporary popular culture, such as comic strips, mundane household objects, posters and advertising materials.

With my collage creations, I am building on the ethos and aesthetics of pop art to focus on digital technologies, and particularly the latest generative AI (GenAI) services from which wealthy Big AI Tech corporations are attempting to profit by marketing them as essential to everyone's lives. Everything about the latest AI moment is 'more, more, more' and 'bigger, bigger, bigger' in service of 'brighter futures'. It is these promotional discourses to which I am drawing attention with my collages. I am highlighting the commodity fetishism around these technologies, the hype and imaginaries evident in the ways that Big AI Tech frantically promotes them, making all sorts of outlandish claims about their benefits and possibilities. The images also serve to emphasise the materialities of 'cloud computing' and GenAI services and the huge resources consumed by building and supporting these technologies that can otherwise feel very ephemeral: computer chips, data servers and hyperscale data centres. The collages were hand-made using Canva Pro, drawing on their archive of images, fonts and editing tools (but avoiding their GenAI tools). Some collages incorporate prints that are available for free use on public archives. The inspirations for these collages are artists George Segal (front cover), Andy Warhol (this page and page 2), Eduardo Paolozzi (page 3), Roy Lichtenstein (page 4), Peter Blake (page 5), Richard Hamilton (page 6) and more recent pop artists Victoria Topping (page 7) and Yayoi Kusama (page 8).

Deborah Lupton, Vitalities Lab, ARC Centre of Excellence for Automated Decision-Making and Society, UNSW Sydney, 2026.
d.lupton@unsw.edu.au

INSANE CLOWN
IS
**GONNA STEAL
YOUR MIND**

GASP!

BOOM!

POW!

POW!

ATOMIC
SIGNS
NEON
Plastic

BAM!

BOOM!

YOUR FUTURE

**UNDER
CONSTRUCTION**

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